

E-WASTE GOOD OR BAD IN INDIA: SUSTAINABLE FUTURE - OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES**Assist. Prof. K. R. Padma¹, Ph.D, K. R. Don², Singanamala Sowjnaya¹**¹Department of Biotechnology, Sri Padmavati Mahila Visvavidyalayam (Women's) University, Tirupati, India²Department of Oral Pathology and Microbiology, Sree Balaji Dental College and Hospital, Bharath Institute of Higher Education and Research (BIHER) Bharath University, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India**ABSTRACT**

The use of electronic devices, machinery for work, communication, and increased business operations are all improved by advances in science and technology. In addition to the effects of using electronic equipment, there is also electronic trash (or e-waste) that occurs from not recycling and a lack of disposable processes. It has an impact on people's way of life, health, and the environment's ecosystem and natural resources. The world's most difficult problem at that point was e-waste. The article discusses the pros and downsides of e-waste, factors of managing e-waste for a sustainable future, problems and opportunities in setting up e-waste management, and some innovative ideas for managing e-waste in India. Further, in order to establish a less-carbon, circular frugality, the article emphasizes critical necessity for stakeholders to be aware of consumer behaviour, global obstacles, and opportunities in this area. The paper concludes by emphasizing the value of a general legal work frame, and licenses, for a makeover of an unorganized area, which directly targets the technologies, the duties of many stakeholders, and entrepreneurial prospects to improve the formal capacity. The article fully supports e-waste recycling chains that are transparent, accountable, and traceable in order to foster a more environmentally friendly atmosphere and safeguard our planet and its natural resources for future generations.

Keywords: *E-waste, Health hazards, Future sustainability, Stakeholders, E-waste management.*

INTRODUCTION

At present situation world has a different type of environmental problems obtaining from manufacturing activities including plastic pollution, industrial waste and electronic waste, etc (Barnes et al., 2009). Recently electronic waste is considered as an important environmental problem (Robinson et al., 2009). E- waste is formed by many aspects (Pant et al., 2012). They are short life cycle of equipment's, poor recycling, sustained enhancing of electronic equipment to reach the demands of developed societies and latest technologies (Tanskanen et al., 2013). In developed countries need to separate the recycled expired electronic equipment which acts as a storage of hazardous chemicals in the environment (Haun et al., 1993).

E-waste used to be regarded as typical rubbish in India. But afterward, the "Hazardous Materials" standards of 2008 were used to treat e-waste (CPCB et al., 2008). Under this, some businesses are developed and engaged in the management of e-waste by scientific and environmentally friendly means by recognized government bodies (Chatterjee et al.2016). Additionally, India's treatment of e-waste is improper due to the involvement of inexperienced workers and the omission of necessary technology as a result of unlawful businesses (Wang et al., 2011). Improper handling of electronic waste leads to severe conditions for both humans and the environment by discharging heavy metals and constituent organics (Cesaro et al., 2017, Rautela et al., 2021, Sankhla et al., 2016, Wath et al., 2010).

With the delivery of E-waste to facilities that are specifically designed to recycle it, technological involvement will give sanitation staff more instruments to promote smooth waste management. In terms of attaining a smart tomorrow in terms of reducing environmental waste, machine learning (ML) applications and robotic automations are seen as the current forerunners. In this article, we look into the employment of a portable, wheeled robot as a garbage truck attachment, with the main objective of sorting and gathering electronic wastes during regular residential trash collection in a city. Individual consumers and civilian houses are the primary targets of our attention. The robot is an addition to the existing labour system, lowering the amount of physical intervention necessary and facilitating simple integration with the city's existing garbage management.

World Wide E – waste generation**Figure-1: Illustrates the countries which generate tonnes of e-waste**

According to research, e-waste exposes the environment to 70% harmful substances and toxins (Hong et al., 2015). Heavy metals like mercury, lead, beryllium, and cadmium are present, along with contaminated PVC plastic and brominated flame retardants that are bad for both human and ecological health. Persistent organic pollutants (POPs), which are also implicated in bioaccumulation and biomagnified food webs, are the primary component of e-waste. (Borthakur et al., 2016).

E-Waste: Good Or Bad?

Now- a-days everyone needs electronic equipment for the purpose of office work, domestic work places like homes, railway stations, bus stations, banks, and other public services. Because it improves the productivity of work, less time taken and get quality products and information. Instead, the consumption of electronics increases dramatically which leads to the accumulation of e-waste (Wu et al., 2011).

Figure-2: Depicts E-waste importance and harmful effects

Then e-waste is recycled and recycled e-waste not only involved in energy conserve, yet it also recycles natural resources such as copper, silver and aluminum (Borthakur et al., 2016).

E- waste metals and its value in market**Figure-3: Rare Earth metals existing in electronic waste and its cost**

Most of these metals are rare earth metals which are present in electronic waste like gadgets, computers, laptops etc. By recollecting and recycling these rare earth metals helps to decrease the mine works. Recycled e-waste helps to prevent air pollution and water pollution (Rautela et al., 2021).

The electronic waste affects the livelihood, human health and environment. The poisonous chemicals notably mutilate the urinary, respiratory, and digestive system as well as degenerate the immune system resulting in several types of cancers (Osako et al., 2004).

Figure-4: Illustrates the health problems and toxic chemicals contaminating Earth's Surface

The toxic and hazardous chemicals are present environment around landfills, contaminating local ground water, damaging atmosphere, the surrounding communities and animals are also affected. Because e-waste is acts as a bioaccumulation i.e., uptake of chemicals in organisms' overtime, biomagnification which means enhancing the concentration of chemicals in food chain as a result of ingestion of other organisms which leads to imbalance in ecosystem and environment. Earlier literature reports have depicted higher concentrations of heavy metals such as chromium, cobalt, iron, copper, selenium & zinc in blood (Caravanos et al., 2013),

These are PHAHs (poly-halogenated aromatic hydrocarbons), a family of chemicals [Brouwer 1995]. These organic substances are listed in the Stockholm Convention's list of 11 chemical groups that make up the persistent organic pollutants (POPs) category. POPs are dangerous, extremely stable, not easily broken down, lipophilic, and bio-accumulative in living things. These substances can travel by air, water, migratory animals, and other means. These can build up in animal, terrestrial, and aquatic ecosystems in addition to human bodies [Harrad 2010]. Polychlorinated biphenyls were found in breast milk, especially in female personnel engaged in the management of e-wastes, and PAH metabolites were found in urine (Feldt et al., 2014; Asante et al., 2011).

Table-1: Hazardous materials existing in e-waste

Substance	Instance in e-waste	Effects on the environment and human health
Halogenated compounds:		
TBBA , PBB, and PBDE	The most extensively used flame retardant for plastics (thermoplastic components, cable insulation), Printed wire boards and casings are currently where you may find TBBA.	can have detrimental long-term consequences on health and, when burned, is fatal immediately
CFC	cooling system, foam insulation	Halogenated material combustion could result in hazardous fumes.
Heavy metals and other metals:		
Arsenic	Light-emitting diodes contain gallium arsenide in traces..	severely toxic and harmful to health in the long run
Barium (Ba)	Cathode Ray Tube (CRT) getters	if wet, may produce explosive gases (hydrogen).
Beryllium (Be)	Power supply units with x-ray lenses and silicon-controlled rectifiers	hazardous if breathed in
Cadmium (Cd)	NiCd batteries that can be recharged, fluorescent materials (for CRT screens), ink and toner for printers, and drums for photocopier machines	acutely toxic and harmful to one's health in the long run
Gallium arsenide	light-emitting diode (LED)	injurious to health
Lithium	Li-batteries	may develop explosive gases (hydrogen) if wetted
Mercury	LCD backlighting fluorescent bulbs, some alkaline batteries, and mercury wetted switches	extremely toxic and harmful to the body over the long term
Nickel	Rechargeable NiCd - batteries or NiMH- batteries, electron gun in CRT	may cause allergic reactions
Rare Earth elements	(CRT-screen) Fluorescent layer	infuriates eyes and skin
Selenium	Older photocopying-machines (photo drums)	exposure to high levels may cause adverse health effects
Zinc sulphide	Rare earth elements are combined inside CRT screens.	poisonous when breathed in
PCB	Condensers, Transformers	Cause cancer and have other negative health effects on the immune system, reproductive system, neurological system, and endocrine system. bio-accumulable and persistent
Lead	Batteries, printed wiring boards, and CRT screens	causes learning difficulties in children by causing damage to the neurological system, the circulatory system, and the kidneys.
PVC	Insulation for cables	Cables processed at high temperatures may produce chlorine, which is transformed into dioxins and furans.
Chromium-VI	Data tapes, floppy-disks	Allergies are brought on by substances that are immediately toxic and harmful to health over time.

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Some neurodevelopment disorders, pregnancy related problems like spontaneous abortions, still births and some studies suggested they observed the DNA damage to the e-workers by expose of toxic chemical substances in e-waste (Kirsten et al., 2013; Wath et al., 2010; Widmer et al., 2005).

Aspects of E-Waste Management for Sustainable Future

Reduce, reuse, and recycle is the primary idea underlying them. By using clever protocols and good maintenance, you may cut down on e-waste as much as feasible (Saoji et al., 2012). Next, try selling or donating any working electronics that are still in working order.

Table-2: E- Waste management and its characteristic features in diverse countries

Country names	Characteristic features				
	Existing System	E -waste specific	Legal restriction on e- waste imports	Financial flow	Actors in the scene
South Africa	Partial Authorized	Absence of e -waste specific	Precise laws not properly applied	Metal scrap dealers paper e-waste	Importers, Traders, consumers, authorizers
India	Mostly unauthorized by all phases	Distinct to e-waste by unauthorized	Banned tough not totally applied	Absence of defined system	Importers, Traders, Consumers , Recyclers
China	Mostly unauthorized yet semi authorized in urban areas	Semi authorized not exactly for e-waste	Imports officially banned	Individuals collect e-waste and are paid	Importers, Traders, Consumers, scrap dealers
Switzerland	Highly authorized	No e-waste Specific	Precise laws	Advanced recycling fee	Importers, Traders, Consumers

If an electronic component can't be fixed, it is recycled. Inform the public and the local populations of the features, toxics, dangerous substances, etc. of electronic equipment trash. Some of the solutions to e-waste include minimising the effects on waste management, controlling and reducing the volume helps to prevent e-waste, reducing waste and pollution, using chemical treatments, biological treatments, or incinerators, burying the remaining lifted items, stopping and banning harmful waste exports, taking off the poisons, and designing for longevity upgrade, repair, and reuse. Government assistance is necessary to support e-waste management groups.

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Among the methods used to remove metal are manual sorting, magnetic separation, reverse osmosis, electrolysis, condensation, electrolytic recovery, filtration, and centrifugation (Pinto et al., 2008). These methods are less effective, damaging to both human health and the environment.

Another method, bio hydrometallurgical, uses bacterial leaching to mobilize metals from fine-grained e-waste in order to recover the solution (Harikrushnan et al., 2016). Pb, Cu, and Sn are mobilized from printed circuit boards using microbes like bacteria and fungus. More than 90% of the available Cu, Zn, Ni, and Al could be leached by *Thiobacillus thiooxidans* and *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* at electronic scrap concentrations of 5–10g/L in the medium. At a scrap content of 100g/L in the medium, *Aspergillus Niger* and *Penicillium simplicissimum* were able to mobilize copper and tin by 65% and aluminum, nickel, pb, and zinc by more than 95%. (Brandl et al., 2001). The industries that use them for manufacturing use them as a raw resource (Gupta et al.2008).It helps to prevent and decrease the disposal of electronic waste.

Opportunities And Challenges In The Construction Of E-Waste Management

Providing knowledge about permits and licenses for processing e-waste management companies, organizations, and stakeholders. Then it helps the prevention of accumulation of e-waste and good to the environment (Hong et al.2015). Various countries follow variety of techniques, infrastructure for e-waste management (Huisman et al.2021). So, international leaders are to test the best techniques and implemented them across the globe (Xue et al., 2017).

It will help to create, awareness of their responsibilities and act accordingly without problems. By implementing green policies like information about the products life span, reduce, reuse and recycle in each and every component of products (Huisman et al., 2021). Creating awareness programs to consumers about the toxic, hazardous, and illegal disposal of electronic waste (Xue et al., 2017).

Following all these things helps to overcome the amount of e-waste generated and processed.

Some Ingenious E-Waste Management Techniques in India

- The first business that the government has authorized is **E-Parisaraa**. It is India's scientific e-waste recycling facility, and its objectives are to lessen pollution, reduce garbage sent to landfills, and recover valuable metals, plastics, and glass using environmentally acceptable methods from waste (Saoji et al. 2012).
- **Earth Sense Recycle Private Limited** which is a biomedical waste handling and management company. It is involved in recycling all types of e-wastes.
- **Trishyiraya Recycling private Limited** Indian company which offers a safe and reliable release of e-waste. Its ground-breaking method of recycling e-waste guards against pollution, contaminating the air, water, and noise.

- **E-Cycling Approaches-Plug-Into E-Cycling** is a collaboration between the Environmental Protection Agency and consumer electronics manufacturers, retailers, and service providers that provide more options for e-cycling unwanted devices through donations and recycling. It also recycled used electronic components and repurposed those components to make new devices. It is involved in the metals' extraction from e-waste. Consequently, it lowers emissions of greenhouse gases, minimizes pollution, and conserves energy and resources for the environment (Saoji et al., 2012.).
- **Bangalore City has e-bins installed.** It is a non-governmental group that led awareness campaigns about e-waste and the need to dispose of it responsibly. By offering toll-free phone numbers to have e-waste collected from homes and recycled, it has done a wonderful service.
- **To handle electronic trash in an environmentally friendly way,** the Manufacturer's Association for Information Technology established the Electronic Recycler's Association (MAIT et al., 2010; MAIT et al., 2011-12).

CONCLUSION

The main aim of this article is to develop in the field of science and technology enhances the usage of electronic equipment for good productivity, easy communication, information transformation, boom to business activities, and modern life style in nowadays. Instead, all these activities increase electronic waste. This e-waste is caused by improper handling waste management, low-skilled workers, less advanced equipment and low recycled e-wastes, etc. Then it affects human health such as damaging the respiratory, urinary, and digestive systems, etc., bioaccumulation and biomagnification are involved in toxic and hazardous chemicals being stored which results in abnormalities in the food chain and it is ingestion by animals and surrounding communities finally imbalance occurs in ecosystem and environment. These effects are inhibited by e-waste management by following basic principles like Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle. Conduction of awareness programs to know about the universal laws, life cycled span, toxic and hazards components, implementing Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) laws to the consumers. To educate stakeholders on the permits and licenses needed for e-waste management. Some proactive businesses, organizations, and government bodies are engaged in e-waste recycling and trash management, which aids in preventing the release of poisonous and dangerous chemicals into the environment and safeguards public health. By taking these actions, you may reduce and even stop the production of electronic trash while also preserving the environment and natural resources for future generations.

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Competing interests

1 The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

2 Consent for publication

Not applicable

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